

Dissecting Glycosyltransferase Activity in Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells to Enforce Cellular Migration

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Preamble

The study of glycans dates back to Emil Fischer's work systematizing the description of hexose sugars by making actual 3D-structures accessible in a 2D-format. Today, roughly a century later, the field of glycobiology is promising as a diagnostic and therapeutic tool. Years of intensive and systematic study have even given rise to the term glycomedicine, demonstrating the great progress and promising future of the field.

Thanks to combined insight, effort and hospitality of Drs. Robert Sackstein, Director of Program of Excellence in Glycosciences and Hans H. Wandall, Professor of Glycomedicine, I was very privileged to spend The Summer of 2016 as a research trainee in The Laboratory of Dr. Robert Sackstein. The purpose of this report is to present and evaluate my research training experience.

Formally, the report will constitute The Master's Thesis of my Medical Degree.

The experiments that I conducted during my recent research training were in accordance with Dr. Sackstein's therapeutical mission, including weekly consultations and written consent agreeing to his intellectual property. Post Doc Nandini Mondal performed routinely supervision and laboratory manager Kyle C. Martin provided technical as well as theoretical assistance.

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Resumé

Formålet med nærværende opgave er at præsentere min erfaring som medicin-studerende og sommergæst i et forskningslaboratorium til enhver med medicinske interesser, intentioner og visioner i et format der opfylder "*Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals*".

Læringsmæssigt havde opholdet to komponenter, hvoraf den ene var at undersøge en specifik kulhydratstruktur og den anden var at udvide mit molekylærbiologiske metodekendskab.

Den specifikke kulhydratstruktur kaldes *the sialylated lewis x binding determinant*, og betegner en struktur der indgår i den klassiske beskrivelse af cellulær migration under såvel normalfysiologiske forhold som sygdomsmæssige processer.

Histologisk er den udtrykt i adskillige humane væv. Dog er den ikke udtrykt i humane mesenkymale stamceller. Rent topologisk er *the sialylated lewis x binding determinant* udtrykt på mange proteiner herunder CD44, hvilket er et protein der grundet dets gennemgribende kompleksitet er interessant at studere i biologiske og fysiologiske systemer. Udvidelse af mit molekylærbiologiske metodekendskab involverede indsigt i to in vitro metoder. Disse metoder er henholdsvis praktisk håndtering af humane mesenkymale stamceller samt enzymatisk behandling af intakte celler, herunder også humane mesenkymale stamceller. Sidstnævnte foregik ved at inducere glykosyleringen af membranbundne proteiner ved anvendelse en metode, der betegnes *exofucosylation*.

Opholdets væsentligste eksperimentelle fund var at ved forsøg på at slukke for fire individuelle glycosyltransferaser i humane mesenkymale stamceller var i stand til at detektere diskrete fænotyper.

Opgaven er inddelt i fem sektioner. Den første del indeholder en generel introduktion til glykobiologi. Den anden sektion forbinder den generelle glykobiologi med det eksperimentelle arbejde, som jeg udførte under mit ophold. Den tredje sektion præsenterer og diskuterer det datasæt, jeg indsamlede under opholdet. I den fjerde sektion fremstilles en syntese af hovedkonklusionerne. Den femte og sidste sektion præsenterer en detaljeret beskrivelse af henholdsvis materialer og metoder, som jeg konstruerede og arbejdede med under opholdet.

Abstract

The aim of the present thesis is to communicate my summer research training experience as a Medical Student to anyone with an intention to treat and a vision to prevent in a format that strives to fulfill the “Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals”.

The two main components of the research training experience were (i) to study one particular classic glycan modification and (ii) to expand my technical experimental repertoire.

The glycan structure in question is the sialylated lewis x binding determinant, which is a structure known to facilitate cellular migration in health and disease.

Histologically, it is expressed in many tissues of man, but it is characteristically absent from human mesenchymal stem cells. Topologically, the sialylated lewis x binding determinant is expressed on many proteins, including CD44, a protein of great biological interest owing to its complexity.

Expansion of my technical experimental repertoire counted two, namely working with human mesenchymal stem cells and *in vitro* enzymatic preparation of intact cells, by enforced cell surface glycosylation benefitting from a method known as exofucosylation.

Scientifically, I was able to detect only modest phenotypes by knockout of four individual glycosyltransferase genes expressed in human mesenchymal stem cells.

The thesis has five sections. The first section is a general introduction to glycobiology with both a structural and a functional focus. The second section links general glycobiology with the experimental work I conducted as a research trainee. The third section presents and evaluates the data that I collected during my training. A synthesis of the main conclusions will be presented in section four. The fifth and final section presents a detailed description of the materials and methods that I prepared and worked with during my stay.

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Theoretical Introduction

Glycobiology at a Glance

Glycosylation is a post-translational modification present on membrane bound proteins and lipids of both pro- and eukaryotes and are categorized depending on their relation to the protein backbone or lipid structure. The glycoprotein family counts N-glycosylation, O-glycosylation and glycosaminoglycans characteristically displaying repeating disaccharide units. Glycosaminoglycans are also qualitatively different from the former two, as they exist both individually and protein bound. Also, glycosaminoglycans are linear and synthesized by a distinct class of enzymes. As with glycoproteins, glycolipids can be modified by the terminal glycan sialic acid. If a glycolipid is sialylated it is called a ganglioside (Ohtsubo & Marth, 2006). The enzymatic machinery responsible for the creation of N- and O-glycosylation resides in the Golgi-apparatus. Phylogenetically, they all belong to the glycosyltransferase family which occupies approximately 1% of the human genome (Rini J, 2009).

Figure 1. Common classes of glycans: Modified from Varki A. 1997. FASEB J.

Downloaded from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1931/figure/ch1.f6/?report=objectonly>

The glycosyltransferases function in a step-wise fashion, where individual sugar moieties or polysaccharides are added to the non-reducing end of the developing glycoprotein or -lipid. At a molecular level glycosylation is unique in that the structures are not directly translated from the genome. In other words, it is neither possible to predict a glycan structure from an amino acid sequence, nor possible to derive the enzymatic cascade that precedes a specific glycan structure. This interdependency between the molecules present in the micro milieu and the evolving glycan structure is termed microheterogeneity. Functionally, post-translational glycan modifications have a substantial impact as actors in biological systems, as they may be mediators of nearly all biological processes including cell adhesion, molecular trafficking and clearance, receptor activation, signal transduction and endocytosis (Ohtsubo & Marth, 2006).

Classical examples of glycoproteins that mediate cell adhesion are the integrins defined by their RGD-binding motif (Arnaout, 1990). Functionally, it has been stipulated and evidentially supported that glycans are implicated in molecular trafficking and clearance by a variant of endocytosis, that is characteristically clathrin-*independent* (Stanley, 2014). A classic example of glycans involved in receptor activation stems from studies of the Ashwell-Morell receptor, which belongs to the family of asialoglycoprotein receptors (Grewal et al., 2008). Other examples that manifest the biological significance of glycosylation in signal transduction has evolved from studies of the Notch receptor, which is a transmembrane protein with inherent catalytic activity facilitating homophilic receptor interactions (Takeuchi & Haltiwanger, 2014).

Glycans at Work: The Multi-Step Paradigm of Cellular Migration

In a clinical-physiological context, the significance of glycans dates all the way back to Karl Landsteiner's discovery of red blood cells' ability to agglutinate and subsequently mapping of the ABO-blood group system (Bayne-Jones, 1931). To date, the field of glycobiology is rapidly evolving as an empirical platform with diagnostic and therapeutical perspectives benefitting from sophisticated and continuously evolving genetic engineering technologies (Galluzzi et al., 2014; Hudak & Bertozzi, 2014).

The multi-step paradigm of cellular migration is an example of a physiological model that is strictly dependent on receptor signaling involving glycan structures.

Specifically, it involves the interaction of selectins expressed on the endothelium and the sialofucosylated lactosamine binding determinant (introduced in greater detail below) expressed on circulating cells, mainly leukocytes. Indeed, the interaction of circulating cells with the endothelial bed is a ubiquitously physiological phenomenon. Examples include cellular homing, a concept originally introduced to explain the observed flux of lymphocytes between blood and lymph (Sackstein, 2012) and conversely recruitment of neutrophils from the marrow to sites of infection in systemic circulation (Borregaard, 2010).

Originally, the multi-step model of cellular migration was developed to describe the extravasation of leukocytes to the vasculature as a physiological component of stress (Springer, 1994). During embryogenesis, the receptor-ligand interactions of selectins and the sialofucosylated lactosamine expressed on circulating cells operate to form cell-cell adhesion responsible for the colonization of lymphoid organs by lymphocytes. Additionally, the sialofucosylated lactosamine is an important mediator of the inflammatory response as well as a structural actor of a malignant hallmark, namely metastasis. In fact, the selectins have been ascribed the primary function of glycan recognition in mammalian immune function (Marth & Grewal, 2008).

Figure 2. The multi-step model of cellular migration: *Sackstein R, Immun. Review, 2009.*

Originally, three consecutive steps defined the multi-step paradigm of cellular migration. It is in the first step that the binding of the sialofucosylated lactosamine and the selectins is prominent. Other important mediators of cellular migration the chemokines (e.g. $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ and IL-1) and integrins (e.g. LFA-1 and VLA-4), operating chemoattractively through G-protein-coupled receptors and binding between opposing transmembrane type I proteins, respectively (Springer, 1994).

Bridge

Experimental Motivation

Based on glyco-biological insights and the conventional description of cellular migration, it is Dr. Sackstein's therapeutic mission to optimize the migration of human mesenchymal stem cell (MSCs) to the bone marrow in order to cure systemic skeletal disease. Scientifically, it is the experimental challenge to enforce cellular migration to tissues where they are needed. Practically, this is attempted by *ex vivo* biochemical engineering of terminal glycan structures on human MSCs and subsequently reintroduction of the cells in to the circulation.

The key feature of the therapeutic mission outlined above is exactly one phenotypical trait of the human MSCs; namely the fact that they lack expression of the sialofucosylated lactosamine. Consequently, it is the hypothesis that induction of sialofucosylated lactosamine epitopes will facilitate enforced cellular migration. Specifically, upon successful induction of the expression the sialofucosylated lactosamine cellular migration is expected to occur in the bone marrow, as the bone marrow microvessels constitutively express E-selectin (Sackstein, 2009).

The Sialofucosylated Lactosamine Determinant

Traditionally, the sialofucosylated lactosamine is also termed the sialylated lewis x, which is abbreviated sLe^x and designated sCD15. The sLe^x binding determinant is a terminal tetrasaccharide characteristically present on membranebound glycoproteins and –lipids of circulating cells. It belongs to the Lewis blood group system originally described in 1946 by Mourant (Mourant, 1946).

The sLe^x binding determinant may be present on both O- and N-glycans of either simple or complex glycans. Additionally, the determinant can be further modified chemically whereby the affinity for its receptors is altered. Specifically, if sLe^x is expressed on core-2 O-glycans and coupled to multiple adjacent tyrosine sulfate and amino acid residues, the binding affinity increases by a factor 1000 (Cummings RD, 2009).

Originally, the sLe^x binding determinant was identified in cancers, as it is frequently overexpressed in carcinomas. By observing sLe^x expression on circulating cells, the overexpression in carcinomas was accompanied by a decrease in expression on circulating cells. In patients diagnosed with cancer, decreased expression of sLe^x on circulating cells has been correlated with poor prognosis. At such, sLe^x is an interesting structure in cancer biology as a trend in expressional alterations has been described on the primary site of malignancy as well as systemically by analysis of cells harboring the vasculature. Structurally, sLe^x is characterized as an oncogene when polyfucosylated (Varki A, 2009).

As with glycoproteins in general, the specific enzymes catalyzing the creation of sLe^x are type II transmembrane proteins that reside in the Golgi apparatus. They work in a stepwise fashion, by transferring one sugar at a time from a specific nucleotide donor

to the non-reducing end of the growing saccharide chain. Specifically, three families of the isoenzymes are involved in the creation of the sLe^x determinant. These are the $\beta(1,4)$ galactosyltransferases, the $\alpha(1,3)$ fucosyltransferases and the $\alpha(2,3)$ sialyltransferases. The addition of fucose to the sialylated type 2 lactosamine is the rate limiting and final step in the synthesis of the sLe^x binding determinant (Lofling & Holgersson, 2009).

In addition, a different group of enzymes catalyze the reverse reaction. Chemically, the reverse reaction results from hydrolysis of the glycoside linkage between two adjacent sugar moieties. The enzymes in question belong to the sialidase, the β -galactosidase and fucosidase families, respectively (Varki A, 2009).

Figure 3. Glycosyltransferases that regulate lactosamine synthesis in human mesenchymal stem cells: Modified from Mondal N. (unpublished).

At the core of the sialofucosylated lactosamine is the β 1-4, acetylgalactosamine moiety, also designated the lactoseaminyl glycan. Within the glycobiological tradition, the β 1-4, acetylgalactosamine moiety is paradigmatic owing to its conservation among vertebrates as well as its impact in biological systems. In fact, the enzyme responsible for the formation of the $\beta(1,4)$ linkage is the most highly conserved glycosyltransferase among vertebrates (Manzella, Hooper, & Baenziger, 1996).

The majority of studies of the sLe^x determinant have been done in conjunction with its counter receptors. Collectively the counter receptors of the sLe^x binding determinant are known as the selectins and are classically described in the context of cell-cell adhesion during lymphocyte migration (Alberts B, 2007).

Explicitly, the selectins are interesting mediators of biological processes as they operate in cell-cell recognition originally identified between leukocytes and endothelial cells. Hence, the selectins are highly relevant structures in the attempt to map human immunological functions (Marth & Grewal, 2008).

Structurally, the selectins belong to the same class of molecules. That is, all of them are examples of C-type lectins, as binding to their opposing ligands is calcium dependent. Traditionally, the selectins have been categorized in three according to their site of expression. Among them are the E- and P-selectins. Together, these two types of selectins termed the vascular selectins, as both are expressed in the

endothelium. Even so, P-selectin is also found in platelets. In fact, it was originally identified in platelets. The third class of selectins is expressed on leukocytes and consequently designated L-selectin. Aside from the site of expression, the selectins differ in expressional regulation. Whereas L-selectin is primarily regulated by enzymatic cell surface cleavage (e.g. TGF- β and ADAM17) E-selectin is transcriptionally regulated with a transcription time between 2 and 3 hours. P-selectin is characteristically stored in intracellular granules of platelets and endothelial cells, being α -granules or Weibel-Palade bodies, respectively. In man, the vascular selectins are constitutively expressed on the endothelium of the bone marrow and the skin (Sackstein, 2009).

Experimental Object

Given the experimental motivation outlined above, the immediate experimental objective of my recent research training was to evaluate the glycosyltransferase activity in the creation of the type 2 sialyl lactosamine glycan structure in human mesenchymal stem cells. Evaluation was assessed by genetic dissection. In particular the evaluation was attempted by disrupting the expression of four individual genes involved in the synthesis of the type 2 sialyl lactosamine glycan structure by application of the CRISPR/cas9 technology.

The target genes were β (1,4) galactosyltransferase 1 (*β 4GalT1*), α (2,3) sialyltransferases III, -IV and VI (*ST3GalTIII*, *-IV* and *-VI*), all of which are implied in the synthesis of the sLe^x binding determinant (see figure 3 for details).

The evaluation was assessed by a genomic analysis of the *β 4GalT1* knockouts and by analysis of the glycan structures present on the cell surface of all four individual knockout populations.

The hypotheses accompanying the experiments were two, corresponding to the two groups of isoenzymes that were targeted. The first hypothesis was that genetic disruption of *β 4GalT1* would result in lower levels of type 2 sialyllactosaminyl epitopes on the cell surface of human mesenchymal stem cells. Thus, consequently to successful knockout and by application of exofucosylation, the phenotype would alter from sLe^x positive to sLe^x negative. Additionally, it was expected that the phenotype would be Le^x negative, as it was stated a priori that synthesis of every glycan structure downstream of the type 2 lactosamine unit would be down regulated consequently to knockout of *β 4GalT1*.

The second hypothesis regarded creation of the sialyltransferase knockouts. Here, it was hypothesized that disruption of *ST3GalTIII*, *-IV* and *-VI* would result in reduced presence of cell surface sLe^x determinants and a corresponding increased presence of Le^x epitopes.

Results

In order to assess potential enzyme redundancy, the relative gene expression levels of galactosyl- and sialyltransferases expressed in biological relevant levels were measured. Measurements were carried out by application of qPCR on genomic DNA isolated from human MSCs of two individual donors (details outlined in Materials & Methods).

In human MSCs the expression levels of $\beta 4GalT1$, -2, $ST3GalTIII$, -IV and -VI relative to $GAPDH$ vary from 0.1 to 10. The least abundant is $ST3GalTIII$ and the most abundant is $\beta 4GalT1$. These are also the measurements that demonstrate the greatest variability, which is emphasized by the height of the pistons. In addition, the assessment demonstrates that $\beta 4GalT1$, $ST3GalTIII$ and $ST3GalTIV$ are expressed at similar levels which roughly corresponds to the expression level of $GAPDH$ (figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Bar chart representing the expression of galactosyl- and sialyltransferase in human MSCs assessed by qPCR.

Abscise: $\beta(1,4)$ galactosyltransferases, $\alpha(2,3)$ sialyltransferases. Isoforms 1, 2, III, IV and VI.

Ordinate (logarithmic): mRNA levels relative to glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase ($GAPDH$)

Each gene was tested on DNA from two individual donors.

Subsequently a panel of knockout cells was generated using the CRISRP/cas9 technology (details outlined in Materials & Methods). In accordance with the results presented above (figure 1.1), the target genes were $\beta 4GalT1$, $ST3GalTIII$, -IV and -VI.

Figure 1.2. Genomic characterization of the $\beta 4GalT1$ knockouts assessed by PCR of the region surrounding the gRNA sequence. Samples, left to right: 100 base pair (bp) ladder, negative control, DNA isolated from transfected MSCs, DNA isolated from non-transfected MSCs (WT). Wells cropped out from the top of the picture.

In order to verify the knockout events, genomic characterization was carried out by PCR amplification of the region surrounding the guide RNA (gRNA) sequence, designed to target exon one of $\beta 4GalT1$ ¹. The forward and reverse primers were designed 247 base pairs (*bp*) apart. Amplification of DNA isolated from the non-transfected cells yields one distinct band. In contrast, amplification of DNA isolated from transfected cells yields two distinct bands. The upper band corresponds to native (non-mutated) DNA, which migrates a distance matching the range from 200 to 300 *bp* consistent with the expected band size of 247 *bp*. In addition, a band between 100 and 200 *bp* is detected by amplification of the DNA isolated from the transfected cells. Assumingly, the PCR product size of this band is smaller (shorter PCR product) than the expected band size consequently to mutated DNA. At such, the genomic characterization indicates successful knockout of $\beta 4GalT1$ (figure 1.2). However, it has not been assessed explicitly whether the discreet phenotypes in the $\beta 4GalT1$ knockouts that were detected (figure 1.3), were actually a consequence of the expected genetic modification. The attempt that has been included (figure 1.2) does not guarantee knockout, as the data does not provide any information on the DNA sequence. In the MSCs, other attempts to do so were initiated (data not included). The major limit was impurity in the isolated DNA (detectable as smear on gel electrophoresis) and too sparse material for proper analysis (< 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ measured by NanoDrop).

¹Initially, genomic analysis of the sialyltransferase knockouts was unsuccessful. As a consequence of the duration of my stay, optimization and successful repetition was not accomplished.

We next performed a phenotypic characterization of selected glycan epitopes expressed on the surface of ultimately about 5.000 knockout cells. The genetic engineered cells were labeled by directly fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) conjugated monoclonal antibodies (mAb) and lectins. Staining intensity was quantified by flow cytometric analysis. Two different reporters were applied. One reporter was HECA-452, which is a mAb that distinctively recognizes the sLe^x binding determinant. The other reporter of choice was Erythrina Cristagalli Lectin (ECL), a lectin that specifically recognizes type 2 lactosamines. Prior to assessment by HECA-452, cells were exofucosylated with fucosyltransferase 6 (FT6). The results from the two reporters correlate as both demonstrate a minimal *decrease* in mean fluorescence intensity (MFI). Explicitly, fluorescence levels were reduced to 87% and 93% of fluorescence levels in non-transfected (WT) cells (figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3. Detection of cell surface sialylated and unsialylated lactosamines in β4GalT1 knockouts.

Left panel: Exofucosylation with FT6, then staining with HECA-452 mAb, specific for sLe^x

Right panel: Erythrina Cristagalli Lectin staining, specific for type 2 lactosamine

MFI: Mean fluorescence intensity

Similarly, knockout of the individual sialyltransferases expressed in human MSCs was attempted by application of the CRISPR/cas9 technology to cells isolated from bone marrow transplant catheters abolished from clinical procedures. The genetic engineered cells were labeled directly by fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) conjugated monoclonal antibodies (mAb) and lectins. Staining intensity was assessed by flow cytometer.

In order to characterize the sialyltransferase knockout cells, we performed a phenotypic characterization of selected glycan epitopes expressed on the surface of about 50.000 knockout cells. The two selected reporters were directly conjugated FITC HECA-452 mAb and anti-CD15 mAb, respectively. As described above, cells were treated with FT6 prior to detection with HECA-452. Prior to characterization by anti-CD15 mAb, cells were neuraminidase treated.

Detection of the sLe^x and Le^x binding determinants demonstrated that knockout of the individual sialyltransferase genes greatly impacted the presence of sLe^x epitopes. The

MFI was reduced to 38%, 26% and 48% of baseline level in knockout of *ST3GalTIII*, *-IV* and *-VI*, respectively. Thus, the data suggests that *ST3GalTIV* is the major sialyltransferase in generation of the sLe^x determinant in human MSCs (figures 1.3 and 1.4). Explicitly knockout of *ST3GalTIV* yields the largest HECA-452 negative population (figure 1.4, left panel).

Figure 1.4. Detection of cell surface sialylated and unsialylated lactosamines in *ST3GalT* knockouts.

Left panel: Exofucosylation with FT6, then staining with HECA-452 mAb, specific for sLe^x

Right panel: Exofucosylation with FT6, then staining with anti-CD15 mAb, specific for Le^x

MFI: Mean fluorescence intensity

Discussion

The results provide evidence that multiple enzymes are involved in the synthesis of sLe^x binding determinant in human MSCs. The data suggests, that there is not a one to one relation between a particular structure (i.e. the disaccharide bond) and a particular enzyme (i.e. a glycosyl- or sialyltransferase). Therefore, a number of biological regulatory mechanisms may explain the discrete phenotypes. In addition, the fact that a number of concerning technical challenges remain unsettled, complicate a rigorous analysis. The biological as well as technical considerations will be covered in greater detail below.

The technical challenges are partly due to the rigorous dependency on appropriate controls. We did not, for instance have an appropriate control in detection of the type 2 lactosamines by ECL (right panel, figure 1.2). Consequently, the data does not assess if staining with ECL of human MSCs correlates with the expected ECL specificity. However, the data suggests that native human MSCs present with type 2 lactosamine binding epitopes, as they are ECL positive (right panel, figure 1.2). Correspondingly, native MSCs are CD15 negative (right panel, figure 1.3). In effect, the majority of type 2 lactosamine epitopes on human MSCs are unfucosylated. Thus,

this piece of data correlates with the fact that native human MSCs express no $\alpha(1,3)$ fucosyltransferases (addendum from Dr. Sackstein). Moreover, as anti-CD15 mAb recognizes the unsialylated type 2 lactosamine (Le^x), the data underscores that native human MSCs are highly sialylated (discussed in greater detail below).

Another technical challenge is that it is notoriously difficult to assess specifically how enzymatic preparation of cells affects the cellular phenotype including viability. Explicitly, prior to detection of the s Le^x binding determinant, cells were exofucosylated and prior to detection of the Le^x binding determinant, cells were neuraminidase treated. Therefore, the three reporters (i.e. HECA-452, ECL and anti-CD15 mAb) are not readily comparable.

The current strategy in dissection of the glycosyltransferase redundancy is strictly dependent on continuous in vitro availability of human MSCs. In effect of being a primary human cell line, the MSCs present are a major experimental opportunity, as they closely resemble the theoretical basis of the enzymatic dissection. However, practically it is not the most efficient way to assay cell surface glycosylation as human MSCs are rarely passed for more than a month in vitro (*ex vivo*). Thus most likely, establishment of a stable knockout cell line is restricted by the limited replication potential of MSCs in culture.

In order to extend the in vitro replication potential of human MSCs, we attempted to optimize the growth conditions by substituting the media component of fetal bovine serum (FBS) for platelet lysate. In casual evaluation by direct light microscopy over a period between 24 and 48 hours, we observed altered morphology manifested as smaller cells and less spindle formation accompanied by accelerated growth. Besides, a considerable limit to the quality of the data is the quantity of cells that were included for analysis. All individual histograms represent counts of less than 5.000 cells. For comparison, it is reported that a cell population of 1×10^6 individual cells is analyzed for publication (Dykstra et al., 2016).

The modest phenotype in the $\beta 4GalT1$ knockout population is a conceivable consequence of the technical challenges outlined above or a manifestation of glycosyltransferase redundancy. It may even be a combination of both.

Taken together, the data suggests that enzymatic redundancy account for lack phenotype in the $\beta 4GalT1$ knockouts as an isoenzyme, namely $\beta 4GalT2$ is expressed in human MSCs (figures **1.1** and **1.2**). A supporting observation is that the present data set identifies that the expression level of $\beta 4GalT2$ is similar to the expression levels of *ST3GalTIII* and *-IV* (figure **1.2**) one of which, presumably, accounts for creation of most sialylated type 2 lactosamines in human MSCs (figure **1.4**).

In sum, enzymatic dissection of sialylated cell surface glycans is internally coherent as MFI in non-transfected human MSCs is equal in the two unrelated measurements (left panels of figures **1.1** and **1.2**, respectively). Further, the data suggests that human MSCs are highly sialylated, as staining of native MSCs with HECA-452 is positive (left panel, figure **1.4**). The current model system does not discriminate the specific

backbone of the adjacent glycan structures. Therefore, the sialic acid may be predominantly expressed on either N-linked, O-linked glycans or glycolipids. For reference (data not included), the abundance of sialic acid on human MSCs was assessed specifically by staining with indirectly FITC conjugated Maackia Amurensis Lectin II (MAL II), a lectin that specifically recognizes $\alpha(2,3)$ sialic acids. Consistently, reporting with MAL II suggests that human MSCs are highly sialylated. Knockout of the individual sialyltransferase genes reduces the MFI to 85%, 43% and 69% (*ST3GalTIII*, *-IV* and *-VI*, respectively) of baseline level corresponding to MAL II staining of non-transfected human MSCs.

Based on the width of the histograms, the data presents an unexpected variation in assessment of the sLe^x and Le^x binding determinants, respectively. Possibly, the variation reflects cellular senescence, as the two sets of experiments were conducted two weeks apart (figure 1.3). Furthermore, literature reports that MSCs express a β -galactosidase activity related to senescence (see Materials & Methods and figure 0.3 for details). Thus, the presence of lactosamine determinants decreases as cell age and at such may account for an altered phenotype unrelated to genetic engineering.

The key step in establishment of a sensitive evaluation of glycosyltransferase activity in human MSCs consists in optimization of the transfection procedure. For enrichment strategies, introduction of a green fluorescence protein (GFP) tag on the cas9 endonuclease enables enrichment based on fluorescent activated cells sorting (FACS) methodologies. Although the technique has been successfully reported (Yang et al., 2015), it does not enable sustained monitoring of target gene expression level as the cas9 endonuclease is only transiently expressed. In contrast, continuous monitoring of the transfection efficiency can be obtained by introduction of a reporter gene at the cleavage site of the cas9 endonuclease. Potentially an even more sophisticated strategy is to generate a human mesenchymal stem cell line deficient of sialylated cell surface epitopes. The perspective can either be obtained by co-transfection of multiple plasmids each targeting the individual genes, construct one plasmid that harbors more than one gRNA or knockout of selected enzymes upstream of the enzymatic pathways involving catalysis of glycosyl- and sialyltransferases, respectively (Steentoft et al., 2014).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the report presents evidence that synthesis of the type 2 lactosamine determinant in human MSCs is a complex and highly regulated process; consistent with conventional evaluation of glycosyltransferase activity and specificity (Wandall et al., 1997). Additionally, the report emphasizes some technical challenges to the experiments (see Discussion for details).

Although only a minor effect was observed in knockout of $\beta 4GalT1$, the transfection resulted in an expected *decreased* presence of type 2 lactosamines epitopes on the cell surface of human MSCs. In addition, it cannot be stressed enough that lack of positive controls to assess $\beta 4GalT1$ knockout phenotype muddles the conclusion even further. Regardless, it appears that $\beta 4GalT1$ is dispensable for creation of type 2 lactosamines in human MSCs. At such a “rescue phenotype” dominated by expression of $\beta 4GalT2$ may explain the minor effect of knocking out $\beta 4GalT1$.

Knockout of the individual sialyltransferases expressed in human MSCs, resulted expectedly in *reduced* presence of sialylated type 2 lactosamines epitopes on the cell surface. Further, the data suggests that although redundantly expressed, the sialyltransferases do not have equal enzymatic capacity. That is, the sialyltransferase knockout data suggests that sialylation of type 2 lactosamine in human MSCs is dominated by activity of ST3GalIV. In comparison, knockout of the sialyltransferases in human MSCs has a greater phenotypic impact than knockout of $\beta 4GalT1$. In sum, we identified at least four enzymes involved in synthesis of the type 2 sialylated lactosamine in human MSCs.

In addition to the rigorous dependency on proper controls, the immediate technical challenges include two. These are optimizing management of human MSCs in vitro and optimizing the transfection procedure per se. The former can be obtained by adjusting the specific media formulation. Although not evidentially supported, a considerable effect was observed by substituting FBS for platelet lysate. Perspectives on optimization of the transfection procedure include application of FACS preceded by introduction of a GFP-tag and inducing the expression of a reporter gene.

According to the biological perspective (see Experimental Motivation for details), the establishment of a robust assay based on the current strategy, will generate a descriptive dataset. Moreover, the therapeutical perspectives demands generation of an operational platform, where a particular physiological effect (i.e. enforced cellular migration) is obtained by genetic engineering of human MSCs. Explicitly, the latter readout is functional. The former is structural. Despite the qualitative difference between the two readouts (i.e. functional and structural), they are dependent on each other as genetic dissection of enzymatic regulation is necessary in order to benefit therapeutically from physiological models assessed biochemically. Thus, genetic dissection of the glycosyltransferase activity in human MSCs demands careful and persistent attention in order to obtain enforced cellular migration and, subsequently differentiation to tissues were they are needed for immunity and tissue repair.

Materials and Methods

Human Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs)

All reported cellular assays throughout were conducted in human mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). Consequently, their cellular characteristics will be introduced briefly. Experimental work with human MSCs has been reported for half a century (Costero, Chevez, Barroso-Moguel, & Pomerat, 1955). They are defined by their ability to give rise to a broad set of differentiated mesenchymal cell types including osteoblasts, adipocytes, myocytes and chondrocytes. At such, they have a robust and characteristic differentiation potential. By definition, MSCs are categorized as non-hematopoietic stem cells. Phenotypically, they are defined by the expression of CD105, CD73 and CD90 and absence of CD11b, CD14, CD45 and CD34. Additionally, there is consensus that human MSCs express CD44 (Uccelli, Moretta, & Pistoia, 2008). MSCs are particularly interesting as a research platform in the attempt to advance therapeutical options for regenerative medicine, as MSCs consequently to their infinite cell cycle have potential to foster tissue repair. In connection to their microenvironment, MSCs also have potent anti-proliferative and -inflammatory effects (Uccelli et al., 2008).

As stem cells age, they alter phenotypically at a molecular level as well as metabolically. MSCs are no exception. For instance expression of the tumor suppressor p53 is part of the mesenchymal stem cell senescence response. Also, MSCs undergo irreversible changes and typically exhibit β -galactosidase activity related to senescence. Physiologically, MSCs have a remarkable capacity of inhibiting the immune response, making them – seemingly – even more promising in facilitating tissue regeneration in man (Dominici et al., 2006).

In culture, human MSCs are adherent, which is an additional defining characteristic of MSCs (Dominici et al., 2006). However, in comparison with other adherent cell lines (e.g. HaCaT cell line (Boukamp et al., 1988)) they are lifted easily. Morphologically, they are characteristically star-shaped and exhibit some similarities with fibroblast. Cells from the average donor may survive *ex vivo* for about 8 passages, corresponding to the order of 40 days (personal observations).

Characterization of Glycosyltransferases Expressed in Human MSCs

Expression levels of the enzymes in question were assessed by quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) and measured relative to the expression of glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) (Schmittgen & Livak, 2008). Amplification of the genes in question was set up for PCR in 12 μ L using the *SYBR*[®] *Select Master Mix* (appliedbiosystems, by Life Technologies). Primers were pre-prepared at a stock concentration of 10 μ M (5 μ M of forward and reverse primer). For reactions, primers were diluted to a final concentration of 1.25 μ M. The PCR templates consisted in cDNA transcribed *in vitro* from mRNA of two individual donors. The relative expression level of each gene was based on the geometric mean derived from replicates of three and was expressed relative to *GAPDH*, serving the

function of a housekeeping gene. The amplification was performed with *The StepOnePlus™ Real Time System* (ThermoFisher Scientific) and analyzed using GraphPad Prism.

Construction of Vectors for Transfection

Plasmid vectors for transfection of MSCs were prepared in accordance with the CRISPR/cas9-technology (Cong et al., 2013). Primers targeted at the genes of interest were designed using the UCSC Genome Browser. Search was limited to exon one and primers were ordered from Applied Biosystems™. By evaluating each set of primers at the database available at *crispr.mit.edu*, optimal on target and minimal off target effects were ensured. The plasmid constructs were analyzed by restriction digestion and sequencing prior to transfection. The plasmid of choice was pX330 (Addgene), which has been designed by the manufacturer such that it harbors sequences encoding nucleation location signals and a promoter upstreams of the modified CRISPR gene locus. For selection purposes, the manufacturer has also designed the plasmid to express an ampicillin resistance gene. The DNA inserts were designed with overhangs compatible with cleavage motive of the restriction enzyme minimizing risk of self-ligation. The restriction enzyme was BbsI (New England BioLabs®). Restriction cleavage was performed in a buffer composed of 50 mM NaCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 10 mM MgCl₂ and 100 µg/mL BSA. Reaction was performed at pH 7.9 at 37°C for 1 hour.

For ligation, 50 ng of linearized plasmid was incubated with 37.5 ng DNA insert corresponding to a stoichiometric ratio 3:1 between insert and linearized vector backbone. As a means to introduce Gibbs energy into the system and initial challenges producing the plasmid targeting the genetic locus of interest, DNA inserts were phosphorylated prior to annealing. Running buffer was 50 mM Tris-HCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM ATP and 10 mM DTT. Reaction was performed at pH 7.5.

For amplification of the ligated plasmid, it was transduced into *One Shot® Stbl3™ Chemically Competent E. coli* (Invitrogen™, by Life Technologies) and cultured on agar plates with ampicillin at 100 µg/mL. DNA was isolated upon binding to a silica membrane and eluted by an increasing salt concentration gradient in accordance with the manufacturer's protocol (©Qiagen). In order to verify insertion of relevant guide RNA (gRNA) into the vector, samples were sent for sequencing prior to transfection (Biopolymers Facility @ Harvard Medical School, <https://genome.med.harvard.edu/>).

Transfection of MSCs

The MSCs were harvested from human donors. Donors were included according to the Human Experimentation and Ethics Committees of Partners Cancer Care Institutions (Dykstra et al., 2016). The mononuclear fraction was isolated by Ficoll-Hypaque density separation, and plated at 2-5 × 10⁶ cells/mL in T-175 culture flasks. Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), 10% platelet lysate and 1 % Antibiotic-Antimycotic (Gibco®, by Life Technologies) diluted as prescribed to a final concentration of 100 U/mL of penicillin and streptomycin, respectively. Cells were incubated at 37°C for 18 hours and washed in PBS, whereby

isolation of the adherent cell population, that is the MSCs, was obtained. Cells were grown confluent in T-175 flasks, corresponding to 500.000 cells per flask. Prior to transfection, cells were lifted with 0.05% trypsin and 0.5 mM EDTA diluted in phosphate-buffered saline (GIBCO® PBS). Transfection was performed using *Lipofectamine® 3000 Transfection Reagent* (Invitrogen™, by Life Technologies) using 3 µg of pre-paired plasmid construct (as described above).

Enzymatic Preparation of Human MSCs

For exofucosylation, cells were treated with recombinant fucosyltransferase 6 expressed in *Pichia pastoris* expression system (internal development). Reaction volume was 30 µL. Reaction buffer was diluted in Hanks Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) from 25X stock (internal formulation). Additionally, GDP-fucose was added to a working concentration of 1 mM GDP-fucose. Cells were treated for 1 hour at 37°C and reactions were stopped by dilution in HBSS. For neuraminidase treatment, cells were treated with *Neuraminidase (Sialidase) from Clostridium perfringens* (Roche). Enzyme was diluted 1:10 corresponding to a working activity of 10 U/mg. Reaction was performed in PBS for 1 hour at 37°C and stopped by dilution with PBS.

Characterization of Transfected MSCs by PCR on Genomic DNA

Media was removed from transfected MSCs and cells were washed. Subsequently, cells were lifted with trypsin as described above. Then, genomic DNA was isolated with *PureLink® Genomic DNA Kit* (Invitrogen, by lifetechnologies) according to manufactures protocol and sample type categorized as mammalian cell lysate. The isolated DNA served as a template in the PCR. Reaction was prepared with volume picomoles of forward and reverse primer, a total of 10 mM dNTPs and 1 µL of DNA polymerase. Reaction volume was 50 µL and PCR was performed in MJ Research PTC-200 Peltier Thermal Cycler DNA Engine Dual Alpha Blocks. Program was initial denaturation, one cycle at 94 for 2 minutes, then 30 cycles of amplification composed of 94°C for 30 seconds, 56°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 30 seconds. Final extension was ensured by one cycle at 72°C for 5 minutes. Amplified PCR products were analyzed on a 2% agarose gel prepared with 3% ethidium bromide. Gel ran at 100 V for 30 minutes. Running buffer was Tris-acetate-EDTA.

Characterization of Transfected MSCs by Flow Cytometry

Upon transfection, cells were re-grown in T-175 flask till a confluency of >80%, correlating with an incubation time of approximately 4 weeks. Of note is that, cellular doubling time was slowed significantly after transfection. Cellular development was monitored on a regular basis by direct light microscopy. When cells were confluent, they were washed and lifted as described above. Cells were divided according to the mode of assessment. For ECL-staining, cells were incubated with *Fluorescein labeled Erythrina Cristagalli Lectin (ECL, ECA)* (Vector Laboratories) diluted 1:4000 in PBS, incubated at 4°C for 30 min. For staining against the HECA-452 epitope, cells were incubated with *FITC anti-human/mouse Cutaneous Lymphocyte Antigen Antibody* (Biolegend®) diluted 1:10 and incubated at 4°C for 30 min. For assessment

of CD15 epitopes, cells were incubated with *FITC anti-human CD15 (SSEA-1) Antibody* (Biolegend®). As a staining control, *FITC Mouse IgM, κ Isotype Ctrl Antibody* (Biolegend®) was used upon dilution 1:50 in PBS. Data was acquired using FC 500 Series Flow Cytometer (Beckman Coulter) and analyzed by *FlowJo*®.

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